

Digi Marketing Training for SMEs in Tangerang in increasing Sales

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ABSTRACT

The rapid development of social media can be used to expand the MSME market. However, not all MSME players know the opportunity to use social media for marketing. Through training and digitalization of MSMEs organized by service activity groups, it can help the community, especially MSME players, to market products through social media. With this work program, it is hoped that marketing can increase its own attractiveness and be able to expand marketing reach. In addition, useful in selling MSME products, the introduction of social media also aims to sharpen people's knowledge about using social media wisely. The results of the work program include increasing knowledge about the use of social media in marketing, as well as how to apply it to MSME actors. In addition, this activity is able to educate MSME players about the advantages and disadvantages of online marketing.

Keywords: Construction; Digi Marketing; Training

INTRODUCTION

Digitalization is a modernization activity by utilizing digital media in its application. Today, digitalization itself is applied in various fields of life, including the field of entrepreneurship. Digitalization plays an important role in terms of entrepreneurship both at the production stage, business management to product marketing because it will be the future of activities (Utami, 2022). From here we know how important digitalization is in entrepreneurship, especially at the marketing stage. Previous studies on MSME actors who began to switch to the use of digital technology such as social media for the development of MSMEs in Indonesia (Setyanto et al., 2015; Maria Nila Anggia & Muhammad Rifki Shihab, 2019; Maria Nila Anggia & Muhammad Rifki Shihab, 2019; Idah & Pinilih, 2020; Anindia Putra et al., 2019; Bakhri & Futiah, 2020; Habibi, 2021). In marketing products, digitalization

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needs to be done because it can help reach a wider range of customers and save time and marketing costs. Not only that, marketing digitalization is considered more promising in terms of revenue if done properly and diligently. Digital marketing is an effort to introduce a brand by using social media applications that can reach consumers in a wide range (Purwana et al., 2017). Digital entrepreneurship is a phenomenon that arises through the development of information and communication technology. Digital business is the sale of products through electronic networks (Guthrie, 2014). In its development, micro, medium and small enterprises have experienced various changes and advances, one of the causes of which is digitalization. The majority of MSME business actors want to practice digital business in their business development (Susanti, 2020). From there, it can be seen that in developing a business, it is necessary to have rigidity in mastering digital technology. A digital development strategy is needed for MSMEs in providing information technology infrastructure, production processes, and market expansion so that small and medium enterprises have competitiveness and can improve their performance (Slamet et al., 2017). Therefore, there is a need for digital skills in entrepreneurship so as to force MSME players to adapt to the increasingly rapid development of digital technology. MSMEs are important players in the development of the local economy in various sectors and are able to create jobs. This activity is able to describe productive economic efforts carried out individually / individually and in groups (Tedjasuksmana, 2014).

Efforts that can be made to apply digital media in entrepreneurship can be done by learning how digital media itself works, both how to use digital media to platforms that can be used to market the products produced. On the other hand, MSME players who do not even know the importance of digital media will certainly find it difficult to win market competition in the current era of industrial digitalization. With the existence of digital media provides benefits including efficiency, convenience, comprehensive information about products, prices that are quite competitive, discounts, product differences (Tiago & Veríssimo, 2014), citing a study by Chayapa & Cheng Lu (Permadi, et al, 2018) states that several factors influence the decision to shop online shopping, namely; Convenience, this factor is important because most people are starting to try to avoid crowds when shopping in shopping centers. Online shopping is a more effective alternative. Completeness of information, with the existence of online shopping access to information is more complete and easier such as by using platforms with a variety of information, rating and review features to improve quality and information. The availability of products and services, just by accessing the website, customers quickly know the availability of goods without going to the store. Cost and time efficiency, the website offers to prospective buyers by comparing prices in several stores. Online shopping model can be done anywhere and anytime.

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Therefore, with the rapid development of technology and wide open business expansion opportunities, support and strive to further advance MSMEs in Tangerang. This is realized by conducting socialization and training for MSME actors with the aim of providing knowledge and knowledge related to what digitalization is and how to apply it in terms of marketing MSME products. The socialization and training activities themselves are expected to be the foundation for MSME actors in running a business by utilizing digital technology appropriately, especially in terms of marketing the products they produce. Digital technology has changed all the character and nature of a more digital-based entrepreneurial model (Nambisan, 2017). In realizing digitization of the marketing sector for MSMEs, start by collecting data on MSMEs in Tangerang. The data collection includes the type of MSME, owner information, production process, income, products produced and income received. The purpose of the data collection itself is to obtain detailed information and description related to MSMEs in Tangerang Village that have the potential to be developed further. In advancing MSMEs in the village is expected to help develop and advance the village, especially MSMEs in the village. From this data, around 15 MSMEs were obtained that have the potential to be more advanced and develop in accordance with the application of digital media. Therefore, the group organizes follow-up activities in the form of socialization and training in online marketing of MSME products with the aim of expanding the reach of product marketing and facilitating marketing activities themselves.

RESEARCH ELABORATIONS

With offline method within 45 days. This activity has been carried out on July 12-August 25, 2023. The group parachuted in the Village. This KKN activity is broadly divided into 5 stages that have been presented in this dibwah picture. The five stages include: determination of the location of activities, exploration of the location of activities, planning and preparation of work programs, realization of work programs, and evaluation of work programs. Location determination The determination of the location that will be the place of implementation of KKN activities is regulated by the Real Work Lecture Implementation Unit (UPKKN0. From the results of plotting the location as a place for KKN implementation for 45 days². Site review The review of the location of the activity is carried out after the division of plotting the location of the activity. This assessment is carried out to find out the situation and environmental conditions that will be used in the implementation of KKN activities, as well as by reviewing this location of students.

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Able to know the potential of the destination area which will be outlined in the work program as a strategy for community development and empowerment. The planned work program is divided into the main work program and supporting work program. The work program supports each other in accordance with the theme "Digitalization of Village Information, Agriculture and Livestock, MSMEs and Creative Economy". The realization of the work program was successfully realized in week 1 to week 5. Work program evaluation This evaluation is carried out to review the activities that have been carried out by recording all obstacles and errors that occur in each work program. With this evaluation, it is hoped that it will be able to become a lesson for the implementation of future activities so that the same error does not occur again. In addition, the evaluation also aims to modify the work program that will be carried out immediately so that it can be carried out properly and efficiently.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Along with the current industrial revolution 4.0, the use of technology, especially digital media, is increasingly widespread in society, especially for MSME players. The use of technology in entrepreneurship itself includes several functions such as the use of digital technology in business management and also the marketing of MSME products. Therefore, the use of digital technology is considered important for business continuity in the current digitalization era. With the application of digital technology, of course, MSME players will be easier and helped in running their businesses and winning competition in the market. The group collaborates with the village to carry out MSME data collection activities with the aim of obtaining detailed data related to the existence of each MSME in the village. The activity was carried out in the first week to the fourth week of the Real Work Lecture activity. Furthermore, in order to educate the importance of marketing and the use of digital media in marketing products, the group also held main activities, namely socialization related to digitalization of MSME marketing Determination of activity locations Review of activity locations Realization of work programs Planning and preparation of work programs Work program evaluation.

With the aim of providing information and knowledge related to digital marketing to MSME actors in the village as well as marketing training activities using digital media such as Tokopedia and Shopee on August 13, 2023. A series of activities carried out by Group students greatly helped the government in realizing and advancing MSMEs in the Village in the era of the industrial revolution. Data collection of micro, small and medium enterprises in the Village Data collection of MSME actors is carried out from week 1 to week 4 of the Real Work Lecture activity. The activity aims to explore detailed information related to MSMEs in the village. The

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focus of the data collection focuses on crucial information for MSMEs which includes information on business owners, production processes, capital and income management, and marketing of the products produced. Data collection activities are carried out by means of interviews and questions and answers directly to business actors in the village. The local government itself also supports the running of these activities by providing data information and addresses of business owners and collaborating directly with students in conducting MSME data collection in the Village. Interviews and questions and answers to MSME actors. The results of this activity know information about MSMEs in the Village, whether they are still running or not. From the results of interviews with business actors through door to door, there are 88 active MSMEs from 92 lists of MSME actors in 2023.

Several MSME players have gone out of business due to the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. This work program can be an initial work program in classifying MSME actors to continue other work programs. It is hoped that with this work program, MSME actors in Trayu Village will be even better in terms of conditioning business actors at the village level. Socialization related to digitalization of MSME product marketing in the Village. In order to foster sensitivity to the importance of marketing and digitalization in MSMEs, group students held socialization activities with the theme of the importance of marketing and the use of digital media in marketing MSME products. The activity was held on August 11, 2023 by inviting local MSME actors who were considered potential to be developed and located at the village hall. With this socialization activity, it is hoped that MSME actors in the village will gain knowledge and an overview of the importance of marketing using digital media in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 which has prioritized the use of technology in various fields. The socialization material was delivered by students with the main discussion, namely MSME marketing. The topic of the socialization activity emphasized the importance of doing the right marketing for a business and the use of digital media such as Tokopedia and Shopee marketplace platforms in marketing MSME products. Implementation of socialization activities for digitalization of MSME marketing at village halls.

The socialization of digitalization of MSME marketing is running smoothly because of the support from the village regarding the work program with the presence of villages and tools when the activity is carried out. MSME actors were very enthusiastic about participating in the work program with questions raised after the speaker finished delivering the material. The results of this activity can increase the knowledge of MSME actors about the importance of social media in product marketing. By presenting 25 MSME players, they are able to educate in terms of good and correct marketing. It is expected that from this work program, MSMEs in rural communities will grow along with increasingly sophisticated technology. Marketing training by utilizing digital media for MSME actors in the Village. One important indicator in

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the success of marketing business products through digital media is the skills of human resources in operating digital technology. Therefore, students held a training for business actors in the village on August 13, 2023 and took place at the village hall as a form of follow-up activity from the previous activity, namely socializing the importance of marketing using digital media.

The training was held with the aim of helping business actors directly in marketing their MSME products using digital media in the form of Tokopedia and Shopee. Activities are carried out by teaching and guiding MSME actors to operate digital media which begins with creating a marketplace account, completing online store data, uploading and setting product prices and disseminating product sales links to potential customers. The results achieved in the community training work program by utilizing digital media for MSME actors are able to apply digital media, both how to create accounts, upload products, to try if there are buyers who check out. Implementation of digital marketing training activities for MSME actors in the Village From the results of this digital marketing training, MSME players are able to sort and choose which social media is suitable for their respective product businesses by considering the range, weight, and durability of the product. Like plastic flower MSME players, after attending digital marketing training, they are able to market their products at prices of around 300-400 thousand with a wide reach and choose social media shopee and tokopedia. With this marketing training, individuals are able to guide MSME actors efficiently in terms of marketing. From this training, MSME actors will get more profitable and advanced economic benefits.

CONCLUSIONS

Activities deployed in the village carry out MSME data collection, socialization and digital marketing training in the context of digitalization and show the development of micro, small and medium enterprises, especially in the field of advice. The realization of the activities carried out is MSME data collection and the implementation of socialization and training on marketing MSME products digitally. Data collection of business actors through door to door there are 88 active MSMEs in the village. This activity was well received by the community, especially MSME actors. Marketing digitalization is one of the strategies in advancing and improving effective and appropriate MSME marketing so that it is expected to help MSMEs in expanding marketing reach and winning market competition. The socialization of MSME marketing digitalization held was carried out by 25 business actors. This series of activities contributed greatly in order to improve the marketing of MSMEs in the Village. MSME players are committed to continuing to grow following the development of the times by applying and

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utilizing digital technology in entrepreneurship even though KKN activities have been completed. The discussion related to this research is still very limited and requires a lot of input, suggestions for the author to further examine more deeply and comprehensively about Training Socialization and Digitalization in MSME Improvement Efforts in Villages.

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